

A microwave assisted synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-ones and thiones using NiFe₂O₄ ferrite as an effective and reusable catalyst

C. A. Ladole, N. G. Salunkhe and A. S. Aswar*

Department of Chemistry, Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University, Amravati-444 602, Maharashtra, India

E-mail : aswaranand@gmail.com

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Abstract : A microwave assisted one pot synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one/thione derivatives in solvent free conditions by using reusable NiFe₂O₄ ferrite as an inexpensive and efficient catalyst is described. The catalyst NiFe₂O₄ ferrite prepared by co-precipitation method followed by calcination, and characterized by XRD, FT-IR, TG-DTA and SEM analysis for evaluating its structure and morphological analysis. Synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one/thione derivatives over NiFe₂O₄ offers several advantages over conventional method such as simple reaction conditions, high product yields, short reaction time and environmentally benign reaction conditions.

Keywords : Biginelli reaction, NiFe₂O₄ ferrite, 3,4-dihydropyrimidine-2-(1H)-ones/thiones, microwave.

Introduction

Multicomponent reactions (MCRs) are economically and environmentally advantageous and occupied a central position in synthetic organic and medicinal chemistry for their high degree of atom economy, applications in combinatorial chemistry and diversity oriented synthesis¹. Dihydropyrimidinones are vital synthons, pharmaceuticals, precursors, calcium-channel blockers and lead molecule for development of new anticancer, antiviral, antitumor, antibacterial, and anti-inflammatory properties²⁻⁴. Some marine alkaloids containing dihydropyrimidine core unit possess an interesting biological properties, e.g. batzelladine alkaloids have been found to be potent HIV gp120-CD4 inhibitors⁵. A synthetic strategy for the dihydropyrimidine nucleus involves one-pot to multistep approaches. The classical Biginelli synthesis is one-pot condensation reaction using β -dicarbonyl compounds with aldehydes (aromatic or aliphatic aldehydes) and urea or thiourea containing catalytic amounts of acidic conditions. However, this method required longer reaction times, harsh reaction conditions and it has also poor yields. Improvements in such syntheses have been sought continuously. In recent years several methods and catalysts have been used for synthesis of dihydropyrimidines. Few of them are bio glycerol based sulfonic acid functionalized carbon catalyst⁶, nano- γ -Fe₂O₃-SO₃H⁷,

acetic acid⁸, sulfated tungstate⁹, NH₄Cl¹⁰, LiBr¹¹, NiCl₂.6H₂O¹², *p*-TsOH¹³, LaCl₃.7H₂O¹⁴ have been reported earlier. However, these processes are quite costlier, time consuming and environmental unfriendly. It has been observed that Ni⁰-nanoparticles use as catalysts for a wide range of applications in organic transformations such as hydrogenation of olefins¹⁵, reduction of aldehydes and ketones¹⁶⁻¹⁸, chemo-selective oxidative coupling of thiols¹⁹ and support for hydrogen adsorption²⁰.

Nanoparticles and magnetically recyclable catalysts have attracted a great deal of attention as effective catalysts in organic synthesis in recent years²¹⁻²⁴. Nickel nanoparticles are also used as a catalyst in various organic syntheses²⁵. Among these catalysts specifically, the ferrites have been studied broadly. It acts as a Lewis acid type catalyst due to presence of acidic site on spinel ferrite. Microwave irradiation organic reactions become more popular during recent years owing to their higher reaction rates, simpler, safer and environment friendly reaction conditions, which may be suitable to be applied in large scale production²⁶⁻²⁹. Therefore, in view of importance associated with this class of reactions, here we report the synthesis of dihydropyrimidines using NiFe₂O₄ ferrite as catalyst for the Biginelli condensation reaction under solvent free conditions. Some advantages of this catalyst are heterogeneous, inexpensive and easy to pre-

pare, which could be recycled during work-up and this reaction can be taken as a kind of green technology.

Results and discussion

Catalytic characterization :

The catalyst nickel ferrite was prepared by literature method³⁰. The phase composition of the sintered sample was analysed by X-ray diffraction pattern (at 500 °C for 2 h). All peaks observed at $2\theta = 27.48^\circ, 31.81^\circ, 35.72^\circ, 43.37^\circ, 45.53^\circ, 53.87^\circ, 56.55^\circ, 62.99^\circ, 66.30^\circ, 75.34^\circ$ clearly indicate the formation of the phase purity of NiFe_2O_4 (JCPDS card 89-7412). It was also observed that, at high calcination temperature, XRD peaks become sharper as a result of shift towards greater crystallinity (Fig. 1). The average crystallite size was calculated using the Scherrer's formula applied to the major intense peaks :

$$D = k\lambda/\beta \cos \theta \quad (1)$$

where, D is the average crystalline size, k the Scherrer constant (0.89), λ is the wavelength of $\text{CuK}\alpha$, β is the full width at half-maximum (FWHM) of the diffraction peaks and θ is the Bragg's angle. The average particle size was to be 25.10 nm.

Fig. 1. Powder X-ray diffraction of NiFe_2O_4 ferrite.

The FT-IR spectrum of catalyst shows bands in a low frequency region ($750\text{--}500\text{ cm}^{-1}$) due to the iron-oxygen stretching modes of tetrahedral and octahedral sites (Fig. 2). The thermogram of NiFe_2O_4 , was recorded in order to assess the changes occurred regarding the phase transition during heat treatment of the sample. The TG curve shows continuous pyrolysis without any break leaving

Fig. 2. FT-IR analysis of NiFe_2O_4 ferrite.

only 11.20% of the substance. The DTA curve shows endothermic reaction (Fig. 3). The SEM images of NiFe_2O_4 are represented in Fig. 4. The images show, tiny crystalline cubes with agglomeration. Higher SEM particle size compared to XRD particle size can be attributed to agglomeration and different principal of the two techniques.

To evaluate the efficiency of the catalyst, the synthesis of ethyl 6-methyl-2-oxo-4-phenyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidine-5-carboxylate (Scheme 1) was performed as a model reaction by condensation of 1,3-dicarbonyl compound, benzaldehyde and urea in the presence of varying amount of NiFe_2O_4 catalyst using various solvents and under different experimental conditions both in the absence and presence of NiFe_2O_4 catalyst and results are given in Table 1.

In order to establish the optimal conditions, first the set of reactions with varying amount of catalyst, solvent and reaction condition were carried out. Initially to check the necessity of NiFe_2O_4 , the reaction was performed in the absence of the catalyst in microwave irradiation under this conditions and where only 21% yield was obtained even with much longer reaction time (Table 1, entry 1). Whereas in the presence of NiFe_2O_4 (4 mol%), under the same experimental conditions significantly enhanced the product yield (Table 1, entry 2). Increasing the amount of catalyst up to 10 mol% improved yield with complete reaction within just 8 min (Table 1, entry 4). Further, increasing the amount of the catalyst reaction did not show any increase in yields. The reaction was

Fig. 3. Combined TG/DTA curves of NiFe₂O₄ ferrite.

Fig. 4. SEM image of the NiFe₂O₄ ferrite at different magnification.

reaction progressed slowly giving alternatively low yield and no improvement was observed above 350 W microwave irradiation. Therefore, all further reactions were carried out under solvent free condition with 10 mol% NiFe₂O₄ as a catalyst at 350 W microwave irradiation. Moreover, we have also compared reaction condition in terms of time and isolated yields with various solid catalyst such as Fe₃O₄, immobilized nickel(II), NiSO₄·7H₂O, NiCl₂·6H₂O and it has been observed that the present catalyst NiFe₂O₄ is a superior one. The NiCl₂·6H₂O (Table 2, entry 4) shows slightly higher yield but it required

Scheme 1. NiFe₂O₄ ferrite as magnetic catalyst for the synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(*H*) ones.

further checked in presence of different solvents, such as ethanol, water, THF and toluene. In the presence of solvents it was found to be reaction was sluggish (Table 1, entries 5–8). The microwave irradiation below 350 W

longer reaction time. After optimization of the reaction conditions, the scope and generality of this protocol with other reactants were examined by using a variety of aromatic aldehydes, β-ketoesters and urea/thiourea. The re-

Table 1. Effect of different extents of NiFe₂O₄ and solvents on formation of compound **4a**^a

Entry	Catalyst (mol%)	Condition/ Solvents	Time (min)	Conversion ^b (%)	Yield ^c (%)
1	–	Microwave/solvent free	23	28	21
2	4	Microwave/solvent free	19	47	40
3	6	Microwave/solvent free	15	70	63
4	10	Microwave/solvent free	8	100	96
5	10	Reflux/ethanol	120	76	65
6	10	Reflux/water	120	83	69
7	10	Reflux/THF	120	42	38
8	10	Reflux/toluene	120	61	56

^aReaction conditions : benzaldehyde : ethyl acetoacetate : urea or thiourea (1 : 1 : 1.5) in solvents and NiFe₂O₄ ferrite (10 mol%) as catalyst. ^bGC conversion%. ^cIsolated yield.

Table 2. Comparative study with different catalyst

Entry	Catalyst	Amount (wt%)	Molar ratio ^a	Condition/ Solvent	Time (min)/ Yield ^b (%)	Reference
1	Fe ₃ O ₄	20	1 : 1 : 1.5	80 °C/solvent free	16/95	31
2	Immobilized nickel(II)	15	1 : 1 : 1	Reflux/EtOH	300/95	32
3	NiSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	10	1 : 1 : 1.5	Reflux/CH ₃ CN	120/80	33
4	NiCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	25	1 : 1 : 1.5	Reflux/EtOH + HCl (1–2 drops)	300/97	34
5	NiFe ₂ O ₄ ferrite	10	1 : 1 : 1.5	Microwave/solvent free	8/96	This work

^aMolar ratio of benzaldehyde : ethyl acetoacetate : urea. ^bIsolated yield.

sults are listed in Table 3. The structural variations in the aldehydes had no significant effect on the yields. However, it has been observed that electron withdrawing groups and electron donating groups having the reaction protocol results in good yields (86–96%). The reaction progress are comparatively faster with aldehydes containing *p*-hydroxy group, it required only 9 min to give excellent yields (Table 3, entry 13). The NiFe₂O₄ also works well even with sensitive aldehydes such as furfural without leading to the formation of any side product (Table 3, entry 9 and 18). Thiourea has been also used with success to provide the corresponding dihydropyrimidin-2(1*H*)-thiones in high yield (Table 3, entries 10–18). Furthermore, when acetyl acetone and thiourea were used as an alternative of 1,3-dicarbonyl compound and urea as the second and the third components (Table 3, entries 19–24). This process ran easily also behaved with similar steric and electronic effects.

In the present work, NiFe₂O₄ ferrite used as an efficient catalyst, the most important aspect is its recyclability.

The NiFe₂O₄ ferrite was easily separated from reaction medium with the help of magnet, and the magnetically recovered catalyst was reused four times under the same reaction condition for preparation of compound **4a** as a model reaction, without any significant loss in activity. The relationship between the number of cycles of reaction and the catalytic activity in terms of yields of product is presented in Fig. 5, and the mechanism for which has also been proposed in Fig. 6.

Experimental

All chemicals were used of analytical grade and solvents distilled prior to their use. The FT-IR spectra were recorded on Shimadzu FTIR-8400 spectrometer equipped with KBr beam splitter. ¹H NMR spectra recorded on a Bruker Avance (300 and 400 MHz) spectrometer using CDCl₃ and DMSO-*d*₆ as a solvent. The surface morphology of samples was examined by direct observation via Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) model (JEOL Model JSM-6390LV). The XRD measurement using Bruker AXS-

Table 3. Synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1*H*)-ones/thiones using NiFe₂O₄^a

Entry	Product ^b	Substrate/Product			Time (min)	Yield (%)	m.p. (°C)	
		R	X	R ₁			Found	Reported
1	4a	C ₆ H ₅	O	OEt	8	96	201–202	201–202
2	4b	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	O	OEt	14	86	202–203	201–203
3	4c	3-OH-C ₆ H ₄	O	OEt	11	90	211–212	210–212
4	4d	4-OH-C ₆ H ₄	O	OEt	10	92	228–229	227–229
5	4e	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	O	OEt	12	89	200–201	200–201
6	4f	3,4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	O	OEt	14	87	206–207	205–207
7	4g	2-OH, 3-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	O	OEt	15	88	232–233	232–233
8	4h	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	O	OEt	10	90	212–213	212–213
9	4i	2-Furyl	O	OEt	11	91	204–205	203–205
10	4j	C ₆ H ₅	S	OEt	10	92	207–209	208–210
11	4k	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	S	OEt	15	87	252–253	251–253
12	4l	3-OH-C ₆ H ₄	S	OEt	15	89	192–193	191–193
13	4m	4-OH-C ₆ H ₄	S	OEt	9	91	171–172	170–173
14	4n	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	S	OEt	14	86	154–155	154–155
15	4o	3,4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	S	OEt	15	87	152–153	152–153
16	4p	2-OH, 3-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	S	OEt	15	86	157–158	156–159
17	4q	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	S	OEt	12	91	185–186	184–186
18	4r	2-Furyl	S	OEt	10	90	226–227	225–227
19	4s	C ₆ H ₅	O	Me	10	88	237–238	236–238
20	4t	C ₆ H ₅	S	Me	12	87	224–225	223–225
21	4u	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	S	Me	12	90	225–226	224–226
22	4v	2-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	S	Me	15	92	154–157	155–157
23	4w	3,4,5-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₂	S	Me	14	91	151–153	152–153
24	4x	3-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	S	Me	12	89	213–215	214–215

^aReaction conditions : aromatic aldehyde (1 mmol); 1,3-dicarbonyl compound (1 mmol); urea or thiourea (1.5 mmol); NiFe₂O₄ (10 mol%).

^bAll products are known and were identified by their melting point, IR and ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra according to literature.

D8 advanced X-ray powder diffractometer with CuK α line ($\lambda = 1.54056 \text{ \AA}$) in the 2θ range from 10–90°. The thermal analysis was performed by using a Perkin-Elmer STA 6000 instrument. Experiments under microwave irradiation were carried out in scientific microwave synthesizer system supplied by Ragatech Electronics having maximum power output of 700 W and 2450 MHz frequency with 10 power levels. The reaction progress was monitored and purity of products were checked by TLC silica gel plates (Merck 60 F₂₅₄) and GC (Netal Model

ULTIMA-2100 with FID detector) respectively at regular intervals. Melting points were measured on a quality digital melting point apparatus.

General procedure for synthesis of nickel ferrite catalyst :

The nickel ferrite was made by co-precipitation method. In which stoichiometric amount of nickel chloride was dissolved in distilled water and allowed to react with sodium hydroxide solution with vigorous stirring. A solu-

Fig. 5. Recyclability of NiFe₂O₄ ferrite.

Proposed Mechanism:-

Fig. 6. Mechanism of synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-ones/thiones using NiFe₂O₄ ferrite.

tion of ferric chloride was prepared in HCl and it was gradually added in the above solution with continuous stirring for 2 h. It was further heated for half an hour at 60 °C and then the reaction mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature. The pH of solution was adjusted to 7.5 by slow addition of 2 N sodium hydroxide solution. The product obtained was filtered, washed with several times with distilled water and dried at 120 °C in oven and subsequently calcined at 500 °C for 5 h. The synthesized nickel ferrite catalyst was characterized by XRD, FT-IR, TG-DTA and SEM analysis for evaluating its structure, and morphological analysis.

General procedure for preparation 4a-x :

The mixture of 1,3-dicarbonyl compound (1 mmol), an aldehyde (1 mmol), thiourea or urea (1.5 mmol) and NiFe₂O₄ (10 mol%) were placed in 100 mL round bottom flask without any solvent and reaction mixture was irradiated in microwave (350 W) for appropriate period of time.

The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC using hexane : ethyl acetate in 6 : 4 ratio (v/v). After the completion of reaction, mixture was diluted with ethanol (20 mL) and the reaction mass was stirred and allowed to cool, the catalyst was removed with the help of magnet, and magnetically recovered catalyst reused for the next four runs. The solid residue was recrystallized from ethanol to give pure final product. All the products are known compounds and were characterized by IR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectroscopic data and melting points and values are compared with literature data.

Spectroscopic data of compounds :

Ethyl 6-methyl-2-oxo-4-phenyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidine-5-carboxylate (4a) :

m.p. 201–202 °C, lit. 201–202 °C; IR (KBr) ν : 3246, 2979, 2937, 1725, 1649, 1464, 781 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 1.14 (3H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, CH₃), 2.35 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.04, (2H, q, *J* 7.2 Hz, CH₂), 5.41 (1H, d, *J* 2.4 Hz, CH), 5.58 (1H, s, NH), 7.26–7.33 (5H, m, Ar-H), 7.71 (1H, s, NH).

Ethyl 4-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-6-methyl-2-oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidine-5-carboxylate (4d) :

m.p. 228–229 °C, lit. 227–229 °C; IR (KBr) ν : 3244, 2980, 2957, 1723, 1648, 1461, 781 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 1.09 (3H, t, *J* 7.04 Hz, CH₃), 2.25 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.95 (2H, q, *J* 7.04 Hz, CH₂), 5.14 (1H, d, *J* 3.04 Hz, CH), 7.23 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.30 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.71 (2H, s, NH), 9.18 (1H, s, -OH); ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 165.1, 151.9, 148.5, 143.6, 131.8, 128.1, 128.5, 98.8, 59.0, 53.4, 17.7, 14.0.

Ethyl 4-(4-methoxyphenyl)-6-methyl-2-oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidine-5-carboxylate (4e) :

m.p. 200–201 °C, lit. 200–201 °C; IR (KBr) ν : 3243, 2956, 2835, 1706, 1650, 1461, 785 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 1.08 (3H, t, J 7.04 Hz, CH_3), 2.23 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.7 (3H, s, O- CH_3), 3.93 (2H, q, J 7.04 Hz, CH_2), 5.12 (1H, d, J 2.7 Hz, CH), 6.74 (2H, d, J 8.56 Hz, Ar- H), 7.13 (2H, d, J 8.56 Hz, Ar- H), 7.42 (1H, s, NH), 8.96 (1H, s, NH).

Ethyl 4-(4-chlorophenyl)-6-methyl-2-oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidine-5-carboxylate (4h) :

m.p. 212–213 °C, lit. 212–213 °C; IR (KBr) ν : 3244, 2980, 2957, 1703, 1649, 1461, 782 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 1.1 (3H, t, CH_3), 2.24 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.96 (2H, q, CH_2), 5.16 (1H, d, CH), 7.22–7.34 (4H, m, Ar- H), 7.55 (1H, s, NH), 9.04 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 165.4, 153.4, 146.5, 142.1, 133.6, 128.8, 127.9, 101.0, 60.1, 55.0, 18.6, 14.1.

Ethyl 4-(furan-2-yl)-6-methyl-2-oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidine-5-carboxylate (4i) :

m.p. 204–205 °C, lit. 203–205 °C; IR (KBr) ν : 3346, 2984, 2959, 1650, 1488, 731 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 1.24 (3H, t, J 7.04 Hz, CH_3), 2.32 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.11 (2H, q, J 7.32 Hz, CH_2), 5.19 (1H, d, CH), 5.85 (1H, s, furan- H), 5.94 (1H, s, furan- H), 6.21 (1H, s, furan- H), 7.21 (1H, s, NH), 7.26 (1H, s, NH).

Ethyl 6-methyl-4-phenyl-2-thioxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidine-5-carboxylate (4j) :

m.p. 207–209 °C, lit. 208–210 °C; IR (KBr) ν : 3329, 2980, 1670, 1574, 1465, 1196 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 0.91 (3H, t, CH_3), 2.09 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.13 (2H, q, CH_2), 4.98 (1H, d, CH), 7.03–7.09 (5H, m, Ar- H), 9.39 (1H, s, NH), 10.05 (1H, s, NH).

Ethyl 4-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-6-methyl-2-thioxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidine-5-carboxylate (4m) :

m.p. 171–172 °C, lit. 170–173 °C; IR (KBr) ν : 3501, 3184, 3016, 1686, 1580, 1482, 1200 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 1.11 (3H, t, J 6.9 Hz, CH_3), 2.24 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.98 (2H, q, J 6.7 Hz, CH_2), 5.08 (1H, d, J 2.3 Hz, CH), 6.69 (2H, d, J 8.1 Hz, Ar- H), 7.01 (2H, d, J 8.1 Hz, Ar- H), 9.34 (1H, s, NH), 9.5 (1H, s, NH), 10.18 (1H, s, OH); MS : m/z 293 ($M+1$) 234, 188.

Ethyl 4-(4-methoxyphenyl)-6-methyl-2-thioxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidine-5-carboxylate (4n) :

m.p. 154–155 °C, lit. 154–155 °C; IR (KBr) ν : 3314, 2985, 1667, 1575, 1461, 1195 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 1.13 (3H, t, CH_3), 2.29 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.73 (3H, s, O- CH_3), 4.01 (2H, q, CH_2), 5.03 (1H, d, CH), 6.86 (2H, d, J 6.7 Hz, Ar- H), 7.13 (2H, d, J 6.7 Hz, Ar- H), 9.56 (1H, s, NH), 10.24 (1H, s, NH).

Ethyl 4-(furan-2-yl)-6-methyl-2-thioxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidine-5-carboxylate (4r) :

m.p. 226–227 °C, lit. 225–227 °C; IR (KBr) ν : 3314, 2987, 1663, 1574, 1451, 1188 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 1.15 (3H, t, CH_3), 2.29 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.05 (2H, q, CH_2), 5.25 (1H, d, CH), 6.13 (1H, s, furan- H), 6.35 (1H, s, furan- H), 7.53 (1H, s, furan- H), 9.62 (1H, s, NH), 10.37 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 174.9, 164.7, 154.5, 145.6, 142.3, 110.3, 106.0, 98.1, 59.4, 47.6, 17.0, 14.0; MS : m/z 267 (M^+) 208, 162.

5-Acetyl-6-methyl-4-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-3,4-dihydropyrimidine-2(1H)-thione (4u) :

m.p. 225–226 °C, lit. 224–226 °C; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 1.67 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.27 (1H, s, CH_3), 3.42 (1H, s, OH), 4.74 (1H, d, J 2.4 Hz, CH), 6.82 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, Ar- H), 6.94 (1H, t, J 7.2 Hz, Ar- H), 7.23–7.18 (2H, m, Ar- H), 9.01 (1H, s, NH), 9.06 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 176.93, 151.06, 130.09, 129.40, 124.72, 121.13, 116.86, 48.47, 47.89, 29.62, 23.24.

5-Acetyl-6-methyl-4-(2-methoxyphenyl)-3,4-dihydropyrimidine-2(1H)-thione (4v) :

m.p. 154–157 °C, lit. 155–157 °C; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 2.07 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.27 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.76 (3H, s, O CH_3), 5.58 (1H, d, J 3.6 Hz, CH), 6.89 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, Ar- H), 7.03–6.92 (2H, m, Ar- H), 7.26 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, Ar- H), 9.35 (1H, s, NH), 10.21 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 195.57, 174.61, 156.65, 144.35, 130.51, 129.74, 127.76, 120.91, 111.83, 109.61, 55.91, 49.54, 30.10, 18.30.

5-Acetyl-6-methyl-4-(3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl)-3,4-dihydropyrimidine-2(1H)-thione (4w) :

m.p. 151–153 °C, lit. 152–153 °C; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 2.16 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.33 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.62 (3H, s, O CH_3), 3.71 (6H, s, 2O CH_3), 5.25 (1H, s, CH), 6.51 (2H, s, Ar- H), 9.71 (1H, s, NH), 10.28 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C

NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 195.47, 174.56, 153.38, 145.06, 138.86, 137.48, 110.51, 104.23, 60.43, 56.28, 54.23, 30.84, 18.65.

5-Acetyl-6-methyl-4-(4-methylphenyl)-3,4-dihydro-pyrimidine-2(1H)-thione (4x) :

m.p. 213–215 °C, lit. 214–215 °C; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 2.12 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.25 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.31 (3H, s, CH_3), 5.23 (1H, s, CH), 7.08–7.14 (4H, d, J 7.6 Hz, Ar- H), 9.7 (1H, s, NH), 10.24 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 195.28, 174.42, 144.84, 140.45, 137.43, 129.62, 126.96, 110.86, 54.02, 30.78, 21.13, 18.67.

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